

RESEARCH AND COLLABORATION ON DATA SCIENCE AND APPLICATIONS

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1. INTRO

MISION

- ▶ The Business Intelligence Center (CEINE) is an academic center for applied research founded in 2011. We seeks to generate:
 - ▶ New knowledge in Chilean and international society (Publications, Patents, Courses)
 - ▶ Train Advanced Human capital
 - ▶ Generate projects in the area
 - ▶ Generate startups

CEINE 2019 - 2020

WHO WE ARE?

OUR PRODUCTIVE CYCLE

STUDENTS BACKGROUND

- PhD in Systems Engineering - (Sup: 5 students)
- Master in Operations Management - (Sup: 2 students)
- Master in Data Science - (Sup: 11 students)

STRONG MATHEMATICAL
MODELING BACKGROUND

STRONG PYTHON FOR DATA
ANALYSIS

Is easy to obtain students, if
we have a good research
topic

THEORETICAL RESEARCH

TOPICS OF INTEREST IN DATA SCIENCE

1. Improvement of Data Science Models through a new Lagrangean decomposition scheme.

In the context of data science, Lagrange decomposition can often be employed in optimization problems.

Optimization problems are ubiquitous in data science; For example, when fitting models, selecting features, or even designing complete systems, it is important to find the set of parameters that maximize or minimize some objective function.

1. IMPROVEMENT OF DATA SCIENCE MODELS THROUGH A NEW LAGRANGEAN DECOMPOSITION SCHEME.

Lagrangean methods can be used to solve these problems more effectively, and the Lagrangean dual function provides a bound on the optimal value. Lagrangean Relaxation involves relaxing some of the constraints and incorporating them into the objective function with the help of Lagrange multipliers, which adjust the penalty for violating the constraints. This transforms the original problem into a simpler one that can be solved more easily.

2.2 CURRENT APPROACHES

For the description of the current approaches, and of the new approach proposed in this work, the following integer linear programming problem (P) with p constraint sets will be considered, each of which with m_k constraints, $k = 1, \dots, p$:

$$(P) \quad \begin{aligned} & \underset{x}{\text{Maximize}} && \mathbf{c}\mathbf{x} \\ & \text{s. t.} && \mathbf{A}^k \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{b}^k, \quad k = 1, \dots, p-1. \\ & && \mathbf{A}^p \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{b}^p \\ & && \mathbf{x} \in \{0, 1\}^n \end{aligned}$$

where the matrices \mathbf{A}^k , $k = 1, \dots, p$ are of order $m_k \times n$, \mathbf{b}^k is a vector of order $m_k \times 1$, $k = 1, \dots, p$, \mathbf{c} is a vector of $1 \times n$, and \mathbf{x} is a vector of order $n \times 1$.

2.2.1 Lagrangean Decomposition

The Lagrangean decomposition of problem (P) (see, for example, [7]), consists of the inclusion of $p-1$ copies \mathbf{y}^k , $k = 1, \dots, p-1$, from the vector \mathbf{x} of n decision variables, to obtain the following problem (P1) equivalent to (P):

$$(P1) \quad \begin{aligned} & \underset{x}{\text{Maximize}} && \mathbf{c}\mathbf{x} \\ & \text{s. t.} && \mathbf{A}^k \mathbf{y}^k \leq \mathbf{b}^k, \quad k = 1, \dots, p-1. && (1) \\ & && \mathbf{A}^p \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{b}^p && (2) \\ & && \mathbf{y}^k = \mathbf{x}, \quad k = 1, \dots, p-1. && (3) \\ & && \mathbf{x} \in \{0, 1\}^n && (4) \\ & && \mathbf{y}^k \in \{0, 1\}^n, \quad k = 1, \dots, p-1. && (5) \end{aligned}$$

If a Lagrangean relaxation of the constraints (3) is defined, using $p-1$ vectors rows of n dual variables $\lambda^k \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $k = 1, \dots, p-1$, you can get the following relaxed problem:

$$(LD) \quad \begin{aligned} & \underset{x}{\text{Maximize}} && \mathbf{c}\mathbf{x} + \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \lambda^k (\mathbf{y}^k - \mathbf{x}) = \left(\mathbf{c} - \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \lambda^k \right) \mathbf{x} + \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \lambda^k \mathbf{y}^k \\ & \text{s. t.} && \mathbf{A}^k \mathbf{y}^k \leq \mathbf{b}^k, \quad k = 1, \dots, p-1. \\ & && \mathbf{A}^p \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{b}^p \\ & && \mathbf{x} \in \{0, 1\}^n \\ & && \mathbf{y}^k \in \{0, 1\}^n, \quad k = 1, \dots, p-1. \\ & && \lambda^k \in \mathbb{R}^n, \quad k = 1, \dots, p-1. \end{aligned}$$

APPLICATION INTO DATA SCIENCE/ML METHODS

Support Vector Machines

The maximal margin (i.e. the largest distance between the decision boundary and the closest instances of each class) defines the optimal hyperplane. Formally, the linearly separable SVM problem is formulated as follows [13]:

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{w,b}{\text{minimize}} && \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 \\ & \text{subject to} && y_i(w \cdot x_i + b) \geq 1, \quad i = 1, \dots, n \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Where $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^p$, $y_i \in \{1, -1\}$ $i = 1, \dots, n$ are the p-dimensional feature vectors and class labels of a given dataset, respectively, w is a p-dimensional vector of weights, and b is the bias.

And for the non-separable case, [13] introduce slack variables $\xi_i \geq 0$ for each data pair, (x_i, y_i) to relax the constraints, leading to a soft-margin SVM problem, formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{w,b,\xi}{\text{minimize}} && \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 + C \sum_{i=1}^n \xi_i \\ & \text{subject to} && y_i(w \cdot x_i + b) \geq 1 - \xi_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, n \\ & && \xi_i \geq 0, \quad i = 1, \dots, n \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

We can apply our method in order to solve this problem faster with oput loosing toom much quality (which is the trade-off we usually have to face)

TOPICS OF INTEREST IN DATA SCIENCE

Uncertainty aversion predicts the neural expansion of semantic representations

Received: 6 May 2022

Accepted: 17 February 2023

Published online: 30 March 2023

 Check for updates

Marc-Lluís Vives ¹, Jeroen M. van Baar³,
Oriël FeldmanHall

Correctly identifying the meaning of a stimulus requires activating the appropriate semantic representation among many alternatives. One way to reduce this uncertainty is to differentiate semantic representations from each other, thereby expanding the semantic space. Here, in four experiments, we test this semantic-expansion hypothesis, finding that uncertainty-averse individuals exhibit increasingly differentiated and separated semantic representations. This effect is mirrored at the neural level, where uncertainty aversion predicts greater distances between activity patterns in the left inferior frontal gyrus when reading words, and enhanced sensitivity to the semantic ambiguity of these words in the ventromedial prefrontal cortex. Two direct tests of the behavioural consequences of semantic expansion further reveal that uncertainty-averse individuals exhibit reduced semantic interference and poorer generalization. Together, these findings show that the internal structure of our semantic representations acts as an organizing principle to make the world more identifiable.

CAN WE REGENERATE THIS BEHAVIOR IN WORD EMMBEDDINGS?

Word embedding in NLP is an important term that is used for representing words for text analysis in the form of real-valued vectors.

Male-Female

Verb tense

Country-Capital

WORD2VEC

two-layer neural networks that are trained to reconstruct linguistic contexts of words.

GLOVE

It is an unsupervised learning algorithm developed by researchers at Stanford University aiming to generate word embeddings by aggregating global word co-occurrence matrices from a given corpus.

IN THE END WE HAVE...

Points: 10000 | Dimension: 16 | Selected 101 points

TEST DIFFERENT ARCHITECTURES FOR EMBEDDING..

Hopfield Network

Transformer

Self Organizing Maps

TO MEASURE IF THERE IS A SEMANTIC EXPANSION SIMILAR TO WHAT IS DISCOVERED BY HUMAN EXPERIMENTS

TOPICS OF INTEREST IN DATA SCIENCE

3. Social Network Analysis & Mining

Representation Learning

- focuses on automatically learning meaningful representations or features from raw data, without the need for explicit human-designed features
- Popular approaches
GANs, Autoencoders, Variational Autoencoders

New algorithms for insight discovery

- For example, we are developing a new algorithm based on a Variational Autoencoder for RL. We use a Hopfield network as a convolutional layer that allow to memorize patterns while reducing dimensionality

Social network evolution

- How a network will evolve (FUTURE).. is it possible to predict how a network will behave based on the known history? (Phd. Thesis Pablo Cleveland)

EXAMPLE: SOCIAL NETWORK EVOLUTION

Concentración en Mineduc contra el fallo del TC (28)
Por [Daniela Day](#), 27 de Marzo a las 16:59 hrs.

★ [Daniela Day](#), 27 de Marzo a las 16:59 hrs.

Hoy el TC decidió reponer el lucro en la educación, permitiendo nuevamente el negocio de instituciones educacionales con las familias de Chile.
Frente a este nuevo escenario de retroceso de años de nuestras demandas estudiantiles, es necesario organizarnos para defender nuestros derechos y manifestar fuerte y claro el rechazo a la resolución del TC y exigir se reponga la prohibición del lucro al ejecutivo, único actor capaz de vetar al TC.

Desde la FECH estamos convocando a una concentración fuera del Mineduc hoy a las 18:30 ([evento](#)).

[Ignorar*](#) [Compartir](#) [Cerrar](#)

↳ ★ [Daniel E. Szmulewicz](#), 27 de Marzo a las 20:31 hrs.

Vayámonos a paro al toque.

[Ignorar*](#) [Compartir](#) [Cerrar](#)

↳ ★ [Agusto Bustos](#), 27 de Marzo a las 23:20 hrs.

skt 1 paro :V

[Ignorar*](#) [Compartir](#) [Cerrar](#)

↳ ★ [Diego Albornoz](#), 28 de Marzo a las 13:25 hrs.

+1

[Padre](#) [Ignorar*](#) [Compartir](#) [Cerrar](#)

↳ ★ [Daniel Maldonado](#), 27 de Marzo a las 22:13 hrs.

Bueno, quién tiene hambre?

[Padre](#) [Ignorar*](#) [Compartir](#) [Cerrar](#)

Propose a model to predict users' content contribution decisions based on their semantic/topic preferences in order to understand the dynamics of competition between different conversation threads for user attention.

PROPOSAL:
Modification of The Leaky, Competing Accumulator (LCA)

LCA is a model from neuroscience. a mathematical and computational model that is used to describe how decisions are made between multiple choices.

PROPOSAL: ELCA

$X_h^{(u)}$: Carga eléctrica acumulada por la alternativa h considerada por el usuario u

$$\omega_{ij}^{(c)} = \begin{cases} \kappa_c & i = j \\ \lambda_c & i \neq j \end{cases}, c \in \{A, B, C, X\}$$

$$dX_h^{(u)}(\tau) = \left[I_{u,s,h}^t - \sum_{j \in \mathcal{TH}_f^t} \omega_{hj}^{(c(u))} X_j^{(u)}(\tau) \right] d\tau + \sigma_h^{(u)} dW_h$$

$$X_h^{(u)}(\tau = 0) = (1 + \gamma)^l - 1$$

01 Competition between alternatives

Parameter λ_c captures interference between brain zones (alternatives)

02 Decay

κ_c captures decay from one alternative over time.

01

03 Habits Formation

Parameter γ Capture the effect that repetition of an alternative has

04

Segmentation

The model parameters depend on the behavior exhibited by the user on the forum or social network

WE CREATED A FRAMEWORK TO DO SO

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND EVALUATION

12 months of publications
4 subforums
4 performance metrics
3 prediction models
1 class imbalance measure

A LOT OF EXPERIMENTS

Best performance:

- ELCA model
- Subforum 6, month 10
- F1 score: 0.947

Average performance:

- ELCA model F1 score: 0.61
- RF model F1 score: 0.19
- SVM model F1 score: 0.21

THE RESULTS

Average Case

Recall	Accuracy	Precision	F-measure
63%	92%	63%	63%

THE RESULTS

Best case

Recall	Accuracy	Precision	F-measure
95%	97%	95%	95%

APPLIED RESEARCH

INDUSTRY & ORGANIZATIONS THAT WORK WITH US

HEALTHCARE

- *Prediction in many ways:*
 - *From clinical records:
Triage, Readmission, leave.*
 - *Prolisomnography Analysis*
 - *From images (MRI):
Parkinson*
 - *Speech & Cognition*
 - *Text: NLP structuring data
or enriching data to predict*

- *Risk models with
representation
learning*

TELCO

- *Mechanisms to
model how network
quality affect the
quality of service*

RETAIL

- *Segmentation
models for ticket
discounts*

EDUCATION

- *Using of BERT model
measure questions
complexity*

EXAMPLE 1

HEALTHCARE

EXAMPLE 1:
ALMOHDITA

*Platform for
realtime
biosignal
monitoring and
respiratory
diseases alarms*

Como es hoy...

Como queremos que sea...

Dispositivos no Invasivos

Dispositivos Biométricos

Research

Monitoreo en Tiempo Real

Modelo Predictivo

Alarmas

Research

Mejores Decisiones del Staff Médico

Acciones Proactivas

Acciones Proactivas

Devices

Part A

Dispositivos Biométricos

Sensors type 1

can capture 23 signals, but is expensive

Monitoring Kit in-hospital

Visualizations of Biometrics History & Predictions

Volver

Ver en Tabla

ALGORITHMS FOR RISK ASSESSMENT

1. Near realtime alarms
2. Short time risk prediction

MONITOR DE PACIENTES

Ficha de paciente **Buscar Paciente** **Monitor** **Agregar paciente** Cerrar Sesión

Tamara RÃos Garnica (123456)

 Buscar:

FICHA	NOMBRE	UNIDAD	RIESGO PCR	DETALLE
123456	Tamara RÃos Garnica	Unidad: Domicilio Sala: 1 Cama:1		
797231	Cecilia CÃrcomo ArÃvalo	Unidad: Lactantes Sala: A Cama:3	Alto	
12345	Sebastian RÃos PÃrez	Unidad: Lactantes Sala: 2 Cama:2	Alto	
0000100	Juan Valderrama Diaz	Unidad: Domicilio Sala: 1 Cama:1	Medio	
0000102	Javiera Leonor Honda Aldunate	Unidad: Domicilio Sala: 1 Cama:1	Bajo	
790014	FRANCO MICCONO RAMIREZ	Unidad: Domicilio Sala: 1 Cama:1	Bajo	
0000101	Juana Salgado Ford	Unidad: Domicilio Sala: 1 Cama:1	Bajo	

PLATAFORMA @HOSPITAL

We began in operation on 2015.

Starting with only one unit of 33 beds.

By 2022 more than 12,000 patients have used the system

Its used in all 7 units of the hospital (160 beds)

About 2500 patients every year

Internet

Server

Internet

EXAMPLE 2

Organizan:

FONDEF
Fondo de Fomento al Desarrollo
Científico y Tecnológico

Colaboradores:

Lahuen
HEALTH

*Hospital Clínico
Dra. Eloísa Díaz I.
La Florida*

ERRORS CAN HAPPEN WHEN PRESCRIBING DRUGS

Medication Errors can occur when prescribing patients

SOLUTION

We develop a platform to detect in realtime those errors to prevent them

-
- We used **377,316** prescriptions from the HLF,
 - Which resulted in **1,490,954** drug prescriptions.
 - These prescriptions contain **382** different medications.
 - We utilized **100,000** prescriptions to evaluate the expert system.
 - With the current computing power, we achieved processing between **1,000** and **1,500** prescriptions per minute.
 - This is excellent since the system needs to perform this task in real-time while the doctor is handing over the prescription to the patient.

NEXT STEPS...

We plan to connect to the National Prescription System. This way we will be able to reach all Chilean public hospitals. More than 12 million people.

EXAMPLE 3

Land Usage Patterns

A general approach

Data Collection

Data sources used in this research

Telecom

Call detail records

880 million records
3 million individuals
77 days

Banking

Credit card purchases

190 million records
100,000 terminals
3 years

Social

Geotagged urban

32 million records
140 cities
17 years

The Telecom Dataset

Call Details Records

Base transceiver station

Caller Phone Number	Callee Phone Number	Caller BTS	Callee BTS	Timestamp	Call duration (seconds)
0012542872	0042478890	BTS00001	BTS00234	2022-04-10 23:15:18	230
0012542872	0056978425	BTS00041	BTS00934	2022-08-17 08:25:13	37
...
...
0085967423	0012457784	BTS02477	BTS00065	2022-09-30 09:55:23	108

The Telecom Dataset

Study Area

Santiago Tessellation

Urban Areas

Rural Areas

Santiago BTS Positions

Urban Areas

Rural Areas

The Banking Dataset

Credit and Debit card records

Point of sale terminal

Greater Santiago

Santiago City

Downtown Santiago

The Banking Dataset

Credit and Debit card records

Static Topic Modeling

Latent Dirichlet Allocation using geo-tagged digital traces

The main objective of this model is to learn Human Behavioral Patterns from digital traces data distribution by inferring latent topics

$$p(\theta, z, \mathbf{a} | \alpha, \beta) = p(\theta | \alpha) \prod_{s=1}^S p(z_s | \theta) p(a^s | z_s, \beta)$$

The exact computation of the posterior in a Bayesian approach is intractable. Instead, Gibb Sampling is used.

Dynamic Topic Modeling

Dynamic topic models using geo-tagged digital traces

The Idea:

- Divide the dataset by time slice
- Start with a separate LDA for each year
- Then add a dependence of each time slice on the previous one

Experiment 1: Stability

Spatial human activity patterns stability

(a) First Half Dataset

(b) Second Half Dataset

Leisure/Commerce Pattern

Stability

(a) First Half Dataset

(b) Second Half Dataset

Rush Hour Pattern Stability

Experiment 1: A spatial comparison

Geographical representation of human behavioral patterns

Residential

Leisure-Commerce

Rush Hour

Offices Areas

Experiment 1: A spatial comparison

Geographical representation of human behavioral patterns

Residential

Leisure-Commerce

Rush Hour

Offices Areas

Muchas Gracias!

